
Globalization and The Phenomenon of Migration From The Perspective of The Child

Marco Antonio Lima da Cruz Filho

Lawyer registered in Brazil, Especialist in International Law

The year 1970 was identified as the “golden age of social science,” marked by discussions about a world-system where the new way of acting by States was linked to the growing influence of international society, no longer allowing for isolationist and authoritarian actions. Not surprisingly, in line with the spirit established by the Bretton Woods system in 1944, the Tokyo Round discussions began in 1973 within the framework of the then General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), whose central theme was the new international economic order, which “had as its primary objective to give more voice and representation to developing countries, bringing the issue of economic development and the equity of world power to the center of discussions.”

At that time, the movement of goods and services across air, water, and land borders intensified, reaching commerce on a truly global scale. Nevertheless, the harmful effects of this new system became evident, notably from the perspective of deterritorialization or denationalization. Thiago Oliveira Moreira points out that the social, economic, political, and cultural factors common in the daily life of a nation have the capacity to produce impressions that wander through different regions, nations, and continents. In this way, the notion of territory is partially broken, strengthening new views on basic postulates of the social sciences, such as the possibility of economic ascension or a better life in another country.

For example, the dissemination of the American Dream with Americanized ideals of success and happiness was propagated by various sectors of the local market, such as the film industry with Hollywood movies. These ideals gradually became a universal object of desire under the strong influence of American culture, values, and politics, a movement called the country's Soft Power, as discussed by Joseph Nye.

It is prudent to note that alongside the state entity, new forces emerged on an international scale, operating through cross-border networks and entities, promoting the unification or rapprochement of internal processes and aligning norms in various areas. An example is the World Trade Organization (WTO), which seeks to address and, when possible, standardize trade rules between nations. Mention should also be made of transnational companies and business conglomerates such as Amazon or Facebook, whose operations exert strong influence on States and sometimes challenge their sovereignty due to their significant economic power and the widespread use of their products by populations.

They also influence the process of economic, political, cultural, and legal interconnection between peoples, using technological innovations as the main resource, which undoubtedly facilitate interaction as pointed out by Dolinger and Tiburcio. Globalization, therefore, in light of the teachings of Thiago Oliveira Moreira, has basic characteristics such as the information technology revolution, the emergence of an international financial system, the reinterpretation of economic relations between nations, the use of a universal language, and the neoliberal ideology. The latter acquires worldwide predominance as an ideology and practice.

The Westphalian State is thus subsumed by a society that no longer adheres to territorial borders—at least not from the individual's perspective. This creates the need for the state entity to amplify and modify its actions towards the citizen, now having to be guided by ideals such as transnational and transcivilizational consciousness as taught by Onuma Yasuaki.

It should be emphasized that the globalization process, in addition to weakening the nation-state, leads to the development of inequalities and contradictions on both local and global scales. These consequences, however, vary among peoples and different locations. It is certain that peripheral nations suffer more from financial capitalism and the market economy compared to more developed countries. This is because a false idea of the universalization of order and consequently of its benefits is transmitted.

The touted “world of free trade” with weak fiscal barriers aims for easy transit of goods, services, capital, and technology. Such freedom does not extend to everyone, especially to the large mass of migrants, and even more so to those still in the development phase, such as migrant children. In this aspect, those labeled by the market as “less qualified” due to ethnicity, color, gender, age, and religion, who are unwanted or do not comply with documentary regulations to stay in a certain place, face severe barriers instead of opportunities, even if they are struggling to survive.

This condition stimulates the submission of migrants to degrading conditions, notably through irregular work and in abusive circumstances of sexual exploitation crimes, and in the case of migrant children, numerous practices of exploitation and persecution

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specific to this group, ranging from military recruitment to child sexual exploitation. Discrimination is a striking factor even if practiced by subterfuges by the state entity or the market. The person who proposes or is forced to move in search of survival is then pre-conceived.

The intention is for them to have, among other factors, monetary power, know-how, and sufficient age to guide themselves, such as the permanent visa for investors given by Brazil to foreigners who invest a certain amount in the national economy. This rule is just one of the many examples of the desired migrant. In the case of migrants, the majority, especially the undocumented ones, are discriminated against by the mentioned “universalization.” This rejection practiced by the State or market is termed by Adela Cortina as “aporophobia,” which is, in brief synthesis, the aversion to the poor.

In this scenario, the migrant child occupies an even more vulnerable position, considering their condition of being in development, which demands extreme attention, and their condition as a migrant, which further aggravates the situation. Providing appropriate treatment and opportunities is essential. As a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, child migration requires not only the creation of solid political frameworks but also the provision of adequate means of social insertion, development, and subsidy.

This is to enable the sustenance and dignified existence of the growing individual, as seen in the development agendas discussed by the United Nations in 1992 and 2015, which are then based on the fundamental principle of human dignity. The issue is of an international nature and requires a global perspective for a solution in respect of the fundamental precepts that grant migrants, and in the scope of this research, migrant children, the most fundamental rights to an adequate life.

Such protection is established internationally by Public International Law, Private International Law, and Human Rights through general and specific treaties due to the condition of being a child and their refugee status.

In any case, after the reading of this work, it is necessary to keep in mind that: 1) States insist on adopting abusive migration policies internally even though they assume agendas in the opposite direction internationally, configuring a violation of International Law; 2) the migrant, although strengthening the economy in receiving nations, is a preconceived figure of desired gender, race, and color. Discrimination, therefore, will be a striking factor in the analysis of measures implemented for migration control, such as detention; and 3) although requiring special treatment to ensure their best interest, the migrant child is not treated as such in nations that use detention as a form of migration control, violating International Law and being once again subject to liability.

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